

Report on Uses and Gratifications Theory

LASWELL / BLUMLER, KATZ & GUREVITCH

(1940s – 1970s)

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i. Introduction

Such studies' central topic is: Why do individuals use media, and what do they use it? (1983; McQuail). This method is founded on the assumption that audience members are aware of media content and which media they can use to satisfy their desires. An influential tradition in media research is the uses and gratifications approach. The study conducted to explain the enormous appeal of certain media contents served as the foundation for the approach's first conception.

The uses and gratifications method places the responsibility for connecting audience members' needs and media preferences squarely on their shoulders in mass communication. It implies that the needs of individuals have an impact. What media they would select, how they would use particular media, and what pleasures the media provide. This method is distinct from previous theoretical viewpoints in that it views audiences as active media users rather than passive information consumers. Uses and gratifications approach is more interested in "what people do with media" than classic media effects theories, which concentrate on "what media do to people" and presume audiences are homogeneous (Katz, 1959).

It enables audiences to utilize media for their purposes and react to it in a way dictated by their social and psychological backgrounds. According to the uses and gratifications approach (Katz et al., 1974a), the media compete with other information sources to satisfy audience needs on both new and conventional mass media. It is one of the most relevant viewpoints for examining why audiences choose to be exposed to different media channels since it provides people with diverse media platforms and content (LaRose et al., 2001).

The method highlights audience choice by evaluating their motivations for utilizing a particular media to exclude others and the various gratifications derived from the media, depending on individual social and psychological needs (Severin & Tankard, 1997).

It gives a framework for comprehending the ways by which media participants selectively seek information or content., corresponding with their requirements and interests, as a broader perspective among communication researchers (Katz et al., 1974a). Audience members then assimilate the content to meet their needs or interests. (Lowery & Nabila, 1983).

The media influences the audience in three stages:

- Strong- Agenda-setting theory, Magic Bullet theory, and propaganda all lend support. The audience is inactive.
- Moderate - Two-flow step theory provides support.
- Weak - Uses and pleasure theory back it up. The audience is engaged.

ii. Origin and History

Elihu Katz has worked as a sociologist as well as a communication researcher. He earned his Ph.D. in Sociology from Columbia University in 1956 and began teaching at the University of Chicago in 1963. He taught sociology and communication at the Hebrew University of Jerusalem for the following thirty years. Katz led the task committee entrusted with introducing television transmission in late 1960 after being invited by the Israeli government. From the 1970s to the 1990s, this experience influenced his subsequent scholarly work on broadcasting and television in leisure, culture, and communication (UPENN, 2001). He joined the faculty of the University of Pennsylvania's Annenberg School of Communication in 1992, where he also oversaw the experimental Scholars post-doctoral research program.

In 1974, Katz and colleague Jay G. Blumler released *The Uses of Mass Communication*, a collection of essays on gratifications. They examined media consumption from a more humanistic perspective. They propose that media users seek out a medium source that best meets their needs and that they have alternate options to meet their demands. Blumler and Katz (1974). They also discovered that media performed societal and individual roles such as monitoring, correlation, amusement, and cultural transmission (Blumler & Katz, 1974).

FIVE BASIC ASSUMPTIONS (Katz et al., 1974)

The audience is envisioned as being engaged. Many initiatives linking need gratification and media choice belong to the audience member in the mass communication process. Other forms of need fulfillment compete with the media. Many mass media use aims can be obtained methodologically from individual audience members' data. While audience orientations are studied on their terms, value judgments regarding the cultural importance of mass media should be suspended.

Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch (1974) suggested that uses and gratifications research concern with following aspects:

This method is founded on the assumption that audience members understand media content and which media they may use to satisfy their desires.

iii. Needs and Gratifications

Katz, Gurevitch, and Haas (1973) developed 35 needs taken from the social and psychological functions of the mass media and put them into five categories:

1. Cognitive needs, including acquiring information, knowledge, and understanding;
2. Affective needs, including emotion, pleasure, and feelings;
3. Personal integrative needs, including credibility, stability, and status;
4. Social integrative needs, including interacting with family and friends; and
5. Tension release needs, including escape and diversion.

Congruously, McQuail's (1983) classification of the following common reasons for media use:

Information

Learning about relevant events and conditions in one's immediate surroundings, community, culture, and the world, seeking assistance on practical issues or opinions, making decisions, and developing confidence through knowledge.

Gratifications sought (GS) and gratifications obtained (GO)

increasing understanding of oneself, developing an understanding of others' situations, social empathy, relating to people, and developing a sense of belonging to establish a foundation for dialogue and social interaction.

Entertainment

avoiding or diverting attention from difficulties in obtaining intrinsic cultural or aesthetic pleasure.

iv. USES AND GRATIFICATIONS THEORY MODEL

McQuail (1994) added another dimension to this definition. He states:

"Personal social circumstances and psychological dispositions together influence both . . . general habits of media use and also . . . beliefs and expectations about the benefits offered by the media, which shape ... specific acts of media choice and consumption, followed by ... assessments of the value of the experience (with consequences for further media use) and, possibly ... applications of benefits acquired in other areas of experience and social activity."

v. Criticisms of Uses and Gratifications Research

Although the uses and gratifications approach is important in communication research, the approach's study has been criticized for its theory and methodology.

According to McQuail (1994), the technique has yet to give much successful prediction or informal explanation of media choice and use. Because much media use is situational and weakly motivated, the technique functions best when investigating certain types of media when motivation may be offered (McQuail, 1994).

The researcher Ien Ang also criticized the uses and gratifications approach in three aspects:

1. It is very individualized, focusing solely on the psychological enjoyment gained from individual media use. The social context of media use needs to be more noticed. This ignores that some media consumption may have nothing to do with enjoyment - it may be imposed on us, for example.
2. There needs to be more emphasis on media content, with academics focusing on why individuals use the media rather than what meanings they derive from it.
3. The method begins with the assumption that the media are always useful to people and may thus implicitly justify how the media are now organized (quoted by CCMS-Infobase, 2003).

References

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